

**VISHAGHANA MAHAKASHAYA: A CLASSICAL AYURVEDIC
DETOXIFICATION FORMULATION WITH CONTEMPORARY
ANTIOXIDANT AND PHARMACODYNAMIC RELEVANCE**

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ayurveda, the ancient Indian system of medicine, emphasizes preventive and curative approaches through natural detoxification and rejuvenation therapies. Within this framework, *Agada Tantra*, the branch concerned with toxicology, explains the principles of counteracting toxins (*Visha*). Acharya Charaka enumerated *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* as one among the fifty *Mahakashayas*, a unique group of ten herbal drugs exhibiting potent *Vishaghana* (antitoxic) activity. Contemporary studies have suggested that the *Vishaghana* action may be correlated with antioxidant and cytoprotective mechanisms at the cellular level. **Objective:** This review aims to present an integrated analysis of the Ayurvedic and contemporary scientific perspectives on *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*, exploring its pharmacodynamics, phytochemical profile, and antioxidant potential with reference to toxicological and oxidative stress mechanisms. **Methods:** A thorough literature review was

performed utilizing classical Ayurvedic texts such as Charaka Samhita, Sushruta Samhita, Ashtanga Sangraha, and Nighantus, in conjunction with contemporary pharmacological and biochemical research. Published data from journals and databases were compiled to interpret

the antioxidant and detoxifying actions of the constituent herbs. **Results:** *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* comprises ten drugs. *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa*), *Manjishtha* (*Rubia cordifolia*), *Suvaha* (*Pluchea lanceolata*), *Sukshma Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum*), *Palindi* (*Operculina turpethum*), *Chandana* (*Santalum album*), *Katak* (*Strychnos potatorum*), *Shirisha* (*Albizia lebbek*), *Sinduvara* (*Vitex negundo*), and *Shleshmataka* (*Cordia dichotoma*) possess predominantly *Madhura*, *Tikta*, and *Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu–Ruksha guna*, *Ushna Virya*, and *Katu Vipaka*. These pharmacodynamic properties exhibit a counteracting potential against *Visha Guna* (toxic attributes such as *Tikshna*, *Ushna*, and *Laghu*). Modern evidence supports their anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and antioxidant roles, with multiple phytoconstituents such as curcumin, alizarin, quercetin, β -sitosterol, and lupeol exhibiting free radical scavenging and detoxifying effects. **Conclusion:** The Ayurvedic concept of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* can be scientifically correlated with antioxidant and cytoprotective mechanisms that prevent oxidative damage to biomolecules. *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* thus offers a promising multiherbal formulation for managing toxin-induced and oxidative stress-related disorders, justifying its relevance for further experimental validation and clinical research in ethnopharmacology.

KEYWORDS: *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*, *Agada Tantra*, Antioxidant, free radicals, detoxification, Ayurvedic pharmacodynamics, oxidative stress.

1. INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda, the science of life, provides a holistic understanding of health, disease, and detoxification. Among its eight classical branches, *Agada Tantra* the science of poisons deals with prevention and management of toxic conditions arising from animate, inanimate, or artificial sources. The Sanskrit term *Agada* denotes “that which destroys poison,” signifying both antidotal and detoxifying medicines. In ancient contexts, poisons included *Sarpa Visha* (snake venom), *Keeta Visha* (insect toxins), *Dushita Ahara* (contaminated food), and *Garavisha* (slow-acting cumulative toxins). In the modern era, the term *Visha* can be correlated with chemical pollutants, heavy metals, drug toxicity, food adulterants, and reactive oxygen species (ROS) that damage biomolecules and cellular integrity.^[1,2]

Acharya Charaka, in *Sutra Sthana* (4/16), enumerated fifty *Mahakashayas* each comprising ten herbs grouped by pharmacodynamic action. Among these, *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* is defined as a cluster of drugs capable of neutralizing *Visha* and protecting *Dhatus* from

degeneration. The concept of *Vishaghana* aligns closely with the Ayurvedic principle of *Vipritarthakari Chikitsa* the therapeutic application of substances possessing properties opposite to those of the toxin.^[3]

In modern biomedical terms, *Visha* can be viewed as any xenobiotic or free radical generating compound that disrupts homeostasis. Free radicals and reactive oxygen species (ROS) are natural by-products of metabolism, yet excessive accumulation leads to oxidative stress, lipid peroxidation, protein denaturation, and DNA damage.^[4] The endogenous antioxidant defense system comprising superoxide dismutase, catalase, glutathione peroxidase, and non-enzymatic antioxidants (vitamins A, C, and E) works to maintain redox balance. Imbalance between ROS generation and antioxidant defense underlies several pathological conditions including cancer, cardiovascular disorders, nephrotoxicity, and neurodegenerative diseases.^[5]

Given the pharmacodynamic properties described by classical texts, *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* may function as a potent Ayurvedic antioxidant formulation. The concept of *Vishaghana* encompasses both macroscopic detoxification (neutralizing external poisons) and microscopic detoxification (protecting cellular integrity), which parallels modern pharmacological mechanisms of antioxidants and hepatoprotective agents. Recent studies have demonstrated the antioxidant potential of its individual components such as *Curcuma longa* and *Rubia cordifolia*, validating the ancient pharmacological wisdom of Ayurveda.^[6,7]

Therefore, the present review attempts to synthesize the Ayurvedic rationale, pharmacognostic identity, phytochemical profile, and pharmacological evidence of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*, correlating its *Vishaghana* action with antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and cytoprotective mechanisms relevant to contemporary toxicology and biomedical research.

2. Classical Overview of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*

2.1. Description in classical Ayurvedic texts

The concept of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* originates from *Charaka Samhita, Sutra Sthana, Shadvirechanashatashriya Adhyaya (4/16)*, where *Acharya Charaka* enumerated fifty *Mahakashayas* or principal groups of drugs based on their predominant *Karma* (therapeutic actions). Each *Mahakashaya* comprises ten drugs that collectively perform a specific pharmacological function.

The verse describing *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* reads as follows.

हरिद्रामञ्जिष्ठासुवहासूक्ष्मैलापालिन्दीचन्दनकतकशिरीषसिन्धुवारश्लेष्मातका इति दशेमानि

विषघ्नानि भवन्ति (१६)^[1]

(च.सू.४/१६)

This *Mahakashaya* is composed of.

1. *Haridra* (*Curcuma longa* Linn.)
2. *Manjishtha* (*Rubia cordifolia* Linn.)
3. *Suvaha* (*Pluchea lanceolata* (DC)C.B. Clarke)
4. *Sukshma Ela* (*Elettaria cardamomum* (L.) Maton)
5. *Palindi* (*Operculina turpethum* (L.) Silva Manso)
6. *Chandana* (*Santalum album* Linn.)
7. *Katak* (*Strychnos potatorum* L.f)
8. *Shirisha* (*Albizia lebeck* (L.) Benth.)
9. *Sinduvara* (*Vitex negundo* Linn.)
10. *Shleshmataka* (*Cordia dichotoma* G. Forst.)

Acharya Sushruta^[2] and *Vagbhata*^[3,4] have also recognized *Vishaghana Dravyas* in various *Ganas* (groups) such as *Anjanadi Gana*, *Patoladi Gana*, and *Rodhradi Gana*, while *Ashtanga Samgraha* explicitly lists *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* with the same ten ingredients. These drugs were used both *bahya* (externally) and *abhyantara* (internally) in various dosage forms including *Swarasa* (expressed juice), *Kalka* (paste), *Kwatha* (decoction), *Phanta* (infusion), and *Hima* (cold extract), depending upon the nature of the toxic insult.

2.2. Ayurvedic interpretation of “Visha” and “Vishaghana”

The Sanskrit term *Visha* derives from the root “*vish*,” meaning “to enter and spread rapidly.” According to *Acharya Sushruta*, *Visha* is characterized by *Laghu* (light), *Ruksha* (dry), *Tikshna* (sharp), *Aashu* (quick-acting), *Vishada* (non-slimy), *Vyavayi*(diffusible), *Vikasi* (spreading), *Sukshma* (minute), *Ushna* (hot) and *Anirdeshya Rasa* (indescribable taste) *Gunas*.^[5] These qualities enable *Visha* to penetrate *Dhatu*s, disturb *Doshas*, and impair *Agni* (metabolic fire). Conversely, *Vishaghana Dravyas* possess antagonistic attributes predominantly *Madhura*, *Tikta* and *Kashaya Rasa*, *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna*, *Ushna Virya* and *Katu Vipaka* which collectively pacify *Kapha* and *Pitta Doshas* and neutralize the *Visha*

Guna. The doctrine of *Vipritarthakari Chikitsa* thus supports the use of substances with properties opposite to those of the toxic agent.^[6]

2.3. Rasapanchaka profile of Vishaghana Mahakashaya

The *Rasapanchaka* (five-fold pharmacodynamic parameters *Rasa*, *Guna*, *Virya*, *Vipaka*, and *Karma*) provides the foundational Ayurvedic framework to understand drug actions. The following summarizes the *Rasapanchaka* of each constituent herb based on classical Nighantus and compiled reviews.^[7,8]

Table 1: Ayurvedic Pharmacological Profile of Vishaghana Mahakashaya.

Drug	Rasa (Taste)	Guna (Attributes)	Virya (Potency)	Vipaka (Post-digestive effect)	Karma (Action)
<i>Haridra</i> (<i>Curcuma longa</i>)	Tikta, Katu	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Kapha-Pittahara, Vishaghana, Varnya, Pitta-Rechaka
<i>Manjishtha</i> (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>)	Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya	Guru, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Raktaprasadana, Shothahara, Vishaghana
<i>Suvaha</i> (<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i>)	Tikta	Guru	Sheeta	Katu	Vata-Kaphahara, Shothahara
<i>Sukshma Ela</i> (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i>)	Katu, Madhura	Laghu, Snigdha, Sugandhi	Sheeta	Madhura	Kapha-Vatahara, Vishaghana
<i>Palindi</i> (<i>Operculina turpethum</i>)	Katu, Tikta,	Laghu, Ruksha, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu	Vatahara, Virechaka, Shothahara
<i>Chandana</i> (<i>Santalum album</i>)	Tikta, Madhura	Laghu, Snigdha	Sheeta	Katu	Raktapittahara, Dahaprashamana
<i>Katak</i> (<i>Strychnos potatorum</i>)	Madhura, Kashaya, Tikta	Laghu, Vishad	Sheeta	Madhura	Vata-Kaphahara, Vishaghana
<i>Shirisha</i> (<i>Albizzia lebeck</i>)	Madhura, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha, Teekshna	Ushna	Katu	Vishaghana, Shothahara
<i>Sinduvara</i> (<i>Vitex negundo</i>)	Katu, Tikta, Kashaya	Laghu, Ruksha	Ushna	Katu	Vata-Kaphahara, Krimighana
<i>Shleshmataka</i> (<i>Cordia dichotoma</i>)	Madhura	Snigdha, Guru, Pichila	Sheeta	Madhura	Pitta-Kaphahara, Vishaghana

Dominant characteristics of Vishaghana Mahakashaya

- **Rasa:** Madhura (33%), Tikta (33%), Katu + Kashaya (34%)
- **Guna:** Laghu (40%), Ruksha (20%), Snigdha/Pichila (14%), Tikshna (6%)

- **Virya:** *Ushna* (50%), *Sheeta* (40%), *Anushna* (10%)
- **Vipaka:** *Katu* (90%), *Madhura* (10%)

These properties establish the formulation as *Kapha–Pittashamaka* and partially *Vatahara*, making it ideal for neutralizing *Visha* that is primarily *Ushna*, *Tikshna*, and *Vyavayi* in nature.^[9]

2.4. Comparative analysis of *Visha Guna* and *Vishaghana Guna*

When the *Guna* (qualities) of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* are compared with those of *Visha*, it becomes evident that certain attributes overlap, whereas others are antagonistic. This dual relationship facilitates the antidotal mechanism *Vishaghana Dravyas* possessing similar *Sukshma* and *Vyavayi* qualities can penetrate the same cellular pathways as toxins, while the opposite *Sheeta*, *Snigdha*, and *Madhura* properties counteract the deleterious effects.^[10]

Table 2: Correlation of *Visha Guna* with *Vishaghana Guna* and Resultant Therapeutic Effects.

<i>Visha Guna</i> (Toxic properties)	Counteracting <i>Vishaghana Guna</i>	Therapeutic Implication
<i>Tikshna</i> (sharp)	<i>Madhura, Snigdha</i>	Soothes tissue irritation, prevents ulceration
<i>Ushna</i> (hot)	<i>Sheeta, Madhura</i>	Reduces inflammatory heat and oxidative damage
<i>Laghu</i> (light)	<i>Guru, Pichhila</i>	Restores stability to depleted <i>Dhatu</i> s
<i>Vyavayi</i> , <i>Sukshma</i> (diffusive, subtle)	<i>Sukshma</i> (diffusive,subtle)	Enables penetration to cellular level for detoxification
<i>Vishada</i> (non-slimy)	<i>Snigdha, Pichhila</i>	Restores mucosal integrity
<i>Ruksha</i> (dry)	<i>Snigdha</i>	Prevents dehydration and cellular membrane damage

Thus, the *Rasapanchaka* analysis justifies the classical categorization of these ten herbs under *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*, demonstrating their intrinsic potential to balance toxicological insults both at the *Dhatu* (tissue) and *cellular* levels.

2.5. Ayurvedic Pharmacodynamics

From the *Dravyaguna* viewpoint, *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* exerts its effect through three major pathways.

1. **Samprapti Vighatana (breaking the pathogenesis):** By counteracting *Dosha* vitiation, restoring *Agni*, and expelling *Visha* through *Shodhana* (purification) processes such as *Virechana* and *Swedana*.
2. **Dhatu Poshana (nourishing tissues):** *Madhura* and *Tikta Rasa* promote *Rasayana* and *Raktaprasdana* actions, replenishing *Ojas* and preventing tissue degeneration.
3. **Visha Nashana (neutralizing toxins):** The combined effect of *Laghu*, *Ruksha*, *Ushna*, and *Katu vipaka* enhances metabolism and detoxification, while *Snigdha–Sheeta* components soothe and heal cellular injury.

This synergistic pharmacodynamic interplay supports the multi-level detoxification process described in *Agada Tantra* from neutralization (*Visha Shamana*) to expulsion (*Visha Visarjana*).

3. Phytochemical and Pharmacological Overview of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*

3.1. General phytochemical rationale

Herbal formulations in *Agada Tantra* are based on synergistic actions of multiple bioactive compounds. The ten herbs of *Vishaghna Mahakashaya* possess a wide spectrum of secondary metabolites such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenolic acids, glycosides, saponins, and essential oils. These phytoconstituents exhibit strong antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, immunomodulatory, antimicrobial, and cytoprotective activities scientifically supporting their *Vishaghana* (antitoxic) action.^[1–3]

The presence of phenolic and flavonoid compounds (e.g., curcumin, alizarin, quercetin, β -sitosterol) enables these plants to scavenge free radicals, inhibit lipid peroxidation, and enhance endogenous enzymatic antioxidants such as catalase, glutathione peroxidase, and superoxide dismutase.^[4] Collectively, they prevent oxidative stress–induced cellular damage analogous to *Visha* action described in Ayurvedic pathology.

3.2. Phytochemical profile and pharmacological activities

Table 3: Major Phytochemical Constituents and Pharmacological Actions of Vishaghana Mahakashaya.

S. No.	Drug (Botanical Name)	Major Phytochemical Constituents	Pharmacological Actions
1.	<i>Haridra</i> (<i>Curcuma longa</i> Linn.)	Curcuminoids (curcumin, demethoxycurcumin), volatile oils (turmerone, zingiberene), polysaccharides	Potent antioxidant, hepatoprotective, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, anticarcinogenic, hypolipidemic, wound-healing; protects against xenobiotic and pesticide toxicity. ^[5,6]
2.	<i>Manjishtha</i> (<i>Rubia cordifolia</i> Linn.)	Anthraquinones (alizarin, purpurin, munjistin), glycosides, xanthopurpurin	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor, hepatoprotective, radio-protective, antimutagenic, blood purifier; scavenges ROS and enhances catalase and glutathione. ^[7-9]
3.	<i>Suvaha (Rasna)</i> (<i>Pluchea lanceolata</i> (DC)C.B. Clarke)	Quercetin, quercitrin, isorhamnetin, pleuchioside, pluchine	Anti-inflammatory, analgesic, spasmolytic, antioxidant, nephroprotective; reduces benzo(a)pyrene-induced oxidative damage. ^[10]
4.	<i>Sukshma Ela</i> (<i>Elettaria cardamomum</i> (L.) Maton)	Cineole, limonene, α -pinene, terpineol, sabinene	Antioxidant, hepatoprotective, carminative, antimicrobial; increases glutathione and detoxifying enzyme (GST) levels. ^[11]
5.	<i>Palindi (Trivrit)</i> (<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso)	Turpethin, coumarin, methylpigenin, luteolin	Anti-inflammatory, purgative, antidiabetic, antioxidant, hepatoprotective; reduces CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity. ^[12]
6.	<i>Chandana</i> (<i>Santalum album</i> Linn.)	Santalalin A & B, pterocarpin, pterocarpol, β -santalol	Antioxidant, cooling, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, hemostatic; protects DNA from genotoxic stress. ^[13]
7.	<i>Katak (Strychnos potatorum</i> Linn.)	Diaboline, brucine, loganin, fatty acids (oleic, palmitic)	Antioxidant, antidiabetic, antiarthritic, antimicrobial; reduces lipid peroxidation and restores hepatic antioxidant enzymes. ^[14]
8.	<i>Shirisha (Albizia lebbek</i> L. Benth.)	Saponins, tannins, flavonoids, albizziagenin, okanin	Antioxidant, anti-allergic, antianaphylactic, hepatoprotective; prevents paracetamol and CCl ₄ -induced hepatotoxicity in rats. ^[15,16]
9.	<i>Sinduvara (Vitex negundo</i> Linn.)	β -sitosterol, casticin, flavonoids, essential oils, vanillic acid	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, neuroprotective, antiallergic, antifertility; reduces adriamycin-induced oxidative damage. ^[17]
10.	<i>Shleshmataka</i> (<i>Cordia dichotoma</i> G. Forst)	Lupeol, β -sitosterol, amyriins, octacosanol	Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, wound-healing, antimicrobial, antiulcer; enhances superoxide dismutase and catalase. ^[18]

3.3. Pharmacological synergy and detoxification mechanisms

The pharmacological synergy of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* lies in the complementary mechanisms of its constituent herbs. Experimental evidence demonstrates that most drugs in this group act via one or more of the following detoxifying and antioxidant mechanisms:

- 1. Free radical scavenging:** Polyphenols (curcumin, quercetin, alizarin) neutralize reactive oxygen and nitrogen species, preventing lipid peroxidation and DNA damage.^[19]
- 2. Enzyme modulation:** Flavonoids enhance glutathione (GSH), catalase (CAT), and superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity, improving endogenous antioxidant defense.^[20]
- 3. Anti-inflammatory action:** Compounds such as curcumin and pluchine inhibit cyclooxygenase (COX) and lipoxygenase (LOX) pathways, reducing inflammatory mediators linked with toxin-induced injury.^[21]
- 4. Hepatoprotection and cytoprotection:** Multiple ingredients (e.g., *Albizia lebbek*, *Operculina turpethum*, *Strychnos potatorum*) demonstrate significant hepatoprotective effects in models of CCl₄ or paracetamol-induced liver damage.^[22]
- 5. Detoxification enzyme induction:** Cardamom and turmeric are shown to enhance glutathione S-transferase (GST) activity and phase II detoxification enzymes, aiding biotransformation and excretion of xenobiotics.^[23]
- 6. Cell membrane stabilization:** Triterpenoids and sterols in *Cordia dichotoma* and *Vitex negundo* strengthen cell membranes, reducing permeability to toxins and preserving mitochondrial function.^[24]
- 7. Chelation and metal detoxification:** Phenolic compounds from *Rubia cordifolia* and *Haridra* chelate heavy metals and reduce oxidative injury due to cadmium and lead exposure.^[25]

The integrated pharmacodynamic result is enhanced *Agni* (metabolic fire) at the cellular level, improved detoxification, and prevention of *Dhatu Dushti* (tissue derangement), thereby restoring homeostasis.

3.4. Evidence from experimental and clinical studies

- *Curcuma longa* has shown dose-dependent increases in SOD and catalase in oxidative stress models, protecting hepatocytes from acetaminophen and pesticide-induced damage.^[26]
- *Rubia cordifolia* exhibits antioxidant and radioprotective activity by upregulating antioxidant enzymes and preventing chromosomal aberrations.^[27]

- *Pluchea lanceolata* demonstrated renal protection against benzo(a)pyrene-induced oxidative DNA damage and improved glutathione content.^[28]
- *Vitex negundo* extract significantly reversed adriamycin-induced cardiotoxicity in animal models, reflecting its systemic antioxidant efficacy.^[29]
- *Cordia dichotoma* fruit extract displayed potent DPPH free radical scavenging activity and reduced lipid peroxidation, confirming its antioxidative role.^[30]

These observations strongly correlate with the Ayurvedic claim of *Vishaghana* (antitoxic) activity, wherein the drugs neutralize and expel *Visha* from the system by opposing its pharmacodynamic attributes.

3.5. Integrative pharmacological interpretation

From an integrated perspective, the antioxidant potential of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* mirrors its *Vishaghana Karma* described in *Charaka Samhita*. *Visha* at the molecular level manifests as oxidative stress damaging *Dhatu*s (tissues) and *Ojas* (vital essence). The formulation's phytochemicals protect cellular integrity by.

- Neutralizing free radicals (akin to *Visha Shamanam*)
- Supporting enzymatic detoxification (akin to *Visha Visarjanam*)
- Repairing tissue damage and restoring *Ojas* (akin to *Rasayana Karma*)

Thus, *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* not only counteracts acute and chronic toxicities but also reinforces antioxidant defense, justifying its potential as a natural polyherbal antioxidant formulation in modern ethnopharmacology.

4. Pharmacodynamics and Mechanism of Action

4.1. Ayurvedic pharmacodynamics (*Dravyaguna* and *Karma* perspective)

According to *Agada Tantra*, the term *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* signifies a composite group of herbs capable of neutralizing the harmful effects of *Visha* (toxins) at both systemic and cellular levels. Each constituent acts through its specific *Rasapanchaka* and *Karma*, yet collectively they achieve *Samprapti Vighatana* (breaking of pathogenesis).

The pharmacodynamic profile of the group can be summarized as follows.

1. **Rasa (Taste):** Predominantly *Madhura* and *Tikta*, these tastes counter *Ushna*, *Tikshna* and *Vyavayi Guna* of toxins.

2. **Guna (Attributes):** *Laghu* and *Ruksha Guna* facilitate penetration to subtle channels (*Strotas*) where toxins accumulate, aiding elimination, while *Snigdha* and *Guru Guna* restore cellular stability.
3. **Virya (Potency):** *Ushna Virya* enhances *Agni* (metabolic fire) and accelerates detoxification; *Sheeta Virya* components cool inflammation and oxidative injury.
4. **Vipaka (Post-digestive effect):** *Katu Vipaka* stimulates digestion and metabolism, promoting elimination of *Ama* (metabolic toxins).
5. **Karma (Actions):** *Vishaghana*, *Shothahara*, *Raktaprasadana*, *Rasayana*, and *Agnideepana Karmas* that collectively neutralize and expel *Visha*.

Thus, the formulation acts at three therapeutic levels.

- **Preventive:** by maintaining balanced *Agni* and *Ojas*, preventing toxin accumulation;
- **Curative:** by neutralizing *Visha* through antagonistic *Rasa-Guna* interaction;
- **Reparative:** by restoring *Dhatu* and *Ojas* depleted by oxidative or toxic insult.

4.2. Mechanistic correlation with modern pharmacology

In biomedical terms, *Visha* can be paralleled to free radicals, xenobiotics, or toxic metabolites that cause oxidative stress and tissue injury. The *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* acts through several overlapping mechanisms supported by modern evidence.

4.2.1. Antioxidant defense modulation

- Polyphenols such as curcumin, quercetin, alizarin, and lupeol scavenge reactive oxygen species (ROS) and reactive nitrogen species (RNS), terminating chain reactions of lipid peroxidation.^[1,2]
- These compounds upregulate endogenous antioxidant enzymes - superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), glutathione peroxidase (GPx), thereby strengthening cellular redox balance.^[3]

4.2.2. Inhibition of inflammatory signaling

- Curcumin, pluchine, and β -sitosterol down-regulate NF- κ B, COX-2, and iNOS expression, decreasing pro-inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-6) that mediate toxin-induced cellular injury.^[4,5]
- *Vitex negundo* and *Albizia lebbek* show antihistaminic and mast-cell-stabilizing effects, explaining their efficacy in allergic and inflammatory toxic responses.^[6]

4.2.3. Hepatoprotective and detoxification enzyme induction

- *Operculina turpethum*, *Albizzia lebbeck*, and *Strychnos potatorum* protect hepatocytes against CCl₄, paracetamol, and lead toxicity by reducing transaminase leakage and restoring hepatic antioxidants.^[7]
- *Curcuma longa* and *Elettaria cardamomum* enhance phase II detoxification enzymes- glutathione S-transferase (GST), UDP-glucuronyltransferase facilitating conjugation and excretion of xenobiotics.^[8]

4.2.4. Cytoprotective and membrane-stabilizing activity

- Triterpenoids like lupeol and amyryns in *Cordia dichotoma* maintain cell-membrane integrity, reduce lipid peroxidation, and prevent mitochondrial dysfunction.^[9]
- Phenolic antioxidants maintain calcium homeostasis and protect against apoptosis triggered by oxidative stress.^[10]

4.2.5. Metal chelation and genoprotection

- *Rubia cordifolia* chelates heavy metals such as lead and cadmium and protects against radiation-induced genotoxicity.^[11]
- *Santalum album* extracts exhibit non-genotoxic and DNA-stabilizing properties, corroborating their classical role in *Visha Shamana*.^[12]

4.3. Stepwise interpretation of *Vishaghana* Action

Table 4: Ayurvedic Detoxification Mechanisms and Their Modern Biochemical Correlates.

Ayurvedic Process	Modern-biochemical correlation	Outcome
<i>Visha Shamana</i> (neutralization of toxins)	Free-radical scavenging, COX-2 inhibition	Reduction of oxidative and inflammatory stress
<i>Visha Visarjana</i> (elimination of toxins)	Hepatic enzyme induction, bile secretion, renal clearance	Enhanced biotransformation and excretion
<i>Dhatu Pushti</i> (tissue nourishment)	Antioxidant protection of membranes, protein repair	Restoration of cellular and tissue function
<i>Oja Vriddhi</i> (enhancement of vitality)	Increased glutathione and mitochondrial efficiency	Improved immunity and metabolic resilience

This alignment illustrates that *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* functions as a multi-target, adaptogenic formulation that modulates oxidative, inflammatory, and detoxification pathways simultaneously.

4.4. Systems pharmacology interpretation

The composite pharmacological network can be understood through the lens of **polyherbal synergy**.

- 1. Primary antioxidants:** *Haridra, Manjishtha, Rakta Chandan* - neutralize ROS.
- 2. Secondary antioxidants:** *Katak, Shleshmataka, Vitex negundo* - enhance enzymatic antioxidant systems.
- 3. Hepatoprotectives and purgatives:** *Operculina turpethum, Albizzia lebbeck* - assist elimination.
- 4. Metabolic regulators:** *Cardamom, Pluchea lanceolata* - modulate metabolic detoxification and inflammation.

This multi-component synergy yields both direct antioxidant and indirect cytoprotective effects mirroring the holistic detoxification approach of Ayurveda.

4.5. Integration with oxidative stress pathophysiology

Table 5: Correlation of Modern Pathogenic Stages with Ayurvedic Concepts and Corrective Actions of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya*.

Pathogenic Stage (Modern)	Ayurvedic Correlation	Corrective action of <i>Vishaghana Mahakashaya</i>
Generation of ROS and lipid peroxides	<i>Visha Utpatti Avastha</i>	Free-radical neutralization by curcuminoids and flavonoids
Damage to cell membranes, proteins	<i>Visha Prasara Avastha</i>	Stabilization by triterpenoids and polyphenols
Inflammatory and hepatic injury	<i>Visha Sthana Samshraya</i>	Anti-inflammatory and hepatoprotective activity
Systemic tissue degeneration	<i>Visha Vyadhi Avastha</i>	<i>Rasayana</i> and <i>Dhatu-pushti</i> actions promoting recovery

Hence, the pharmacodynamic actions described in *Charaka Samhita* as *Vishaghana*, *Shothahara*, and *Rasayana* find direct biochemical counterparts in anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, and regenerative mechanisms demonstrated by modern studies.

5. DISCUSSION

The Ayurvedic pharmacological concept of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* offers a remarkable example of ancient drug classification based on functional and therapeutic properties. This group of ten herbal drugs was formulated by *Acharya Charaka* not merely for counteracting poisons but for maintaining physiological purity and cellular homeostasis. Modern

biochemical studies have begun to uncover molecular pathways that justify these traditional observations.

5.1. Ayurvedic interpretation in the context of oxidative stress

In Ayurveda, *Visha* represents any substance or condition that rapidly disrupts the equilibrium of *Doshas*, *Dhatus*, and *Agni*. The progression of *Visha Vyadhi* (toxic manifestation) can be compared with oxidative stress in modern pathology, where free radicals and reactive oxygen species lead to systemic imbalance. The *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* counters this through opposite qualities (*Guna–Viparaya*) for instance, its *Madhura* and *Sheeta* properties neutralize *Tikshna* and *Ushna Guna* of toxins, while *Tikta* and *Kashaya Rasa* aid in detoxification and tissue healing.

5.2. Modern scientific correlation

Scientific validation of the constituent herbs provides a strong foundation for correlating *Vishaghana* activity with antioxidant and cytoprotective mechanisms. Numerous experimental studies demonstrate that the ingredients of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* reduce lipid peroxidation, prevent DNA damage, and upregulate antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT), and glutathione peroxidase (GPx).

The collective pharmacological actions such as hepatoprotection, anti-inflammatory response, membrane stabilization, and enzyme induction align closely with the *Agadakarman* principles of neutralizing (*Visha Shamanam*), eliminating (*Visha Visarjanam*), and restoring vitality (*Oja Vardhanam*). The synergy among these plants ensures multi-target protection against toxic injuries and metabolic stressors.

5.3. Pharmacodynamic synergy and therapeutic implications

The concept of *Mahakashaya* represents not a random combination but a pharmacodynamically harmonized grouping. Each drug contributes unique yet complementary actions.

- *Curcuma longa* and *Rubia cordifolia* provide potent antioxidant and anti-inflammatory effects.
- *Albizia lebbek* and *Vitex negundo* stabilize mast cells and enhance hepatic detoxification.
- *Operculina turpethum* acts as a gentle purgative, facilitating toxin elimination.

- *Cordia dichotoma* and *Strychnos potatorum* reinforce tissue integrity and improve enzymatic detoxification.

This multi-dimensional pharmacology reflects a systems-based approach consistent with modern *polyherbal synergy* and *network pharmacology* principles. The group therefore acts not only as an antidote but as a restorative *Rasayana*, promoting resilience against oxidative and toxic insults.

5.4. Experimental validation and translational potential

Pre-clinical and in-vitro data highlight significant antioxidant potential of individual drugs within the group. However, integrated studies on the combined formulation remain limited. A recent pharmacodynamic investigation demonstrated enhanced antioxidant and nephroprotective activity of *Vishaghana Mahakashaya* in cisplatin-induced nephrotoxicity, supporting its *Agadakarman* role.^[1] This substantiates its translational potential for managing toxic conditions such as heavy metal exposure, drug-induced organ damage, and inflammatory oxidative disorders.

Further *in-vivo* and *clinical* investigations are warranted to.

- Elucidate synergistic interactions between constituent phytochemicals.
- Determine optimal extraction and standardization protocols.
- Validate its efficacy and safety through randomized controlled trials.

Integration of Ayurvedic wisdom with contemporary pharmacological research can thus open avenues for developing standardized phytopharmaceuticals for detoxification and oxidative stress-related diseases.

6. CONCLUSION

Vishaghana Mahakashaya represents a timeless formulation embodying the Ayurvedic philosophy of holistic detoxification. Its ten constituent herbs exhibit complementary *Rasa*, *Guna*, and *Virya*, making it uniquely suited to counteract *Visha* (toxins) and restore systemic equilibrium. Modern pharmacological studies reveal that these herbs possess potent antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, hepatoprotective, and cytoprotective properties, validating their classical *Vishaghana* role.

By correlating *Visha* with oxidative stress and *Vishaghana* with antioxidant and detoxification mechanisms, this review underscores the scientific plausibility of traditional

Ayurvedic classifications. The formulation offers a promising foundation for developing multi-target herbal therapeutics in the management of toxin-induced and oxidative stress-mediated diseases. Future research focusing on mechanistic validation, standardization, and clinical evaluation will further enhance its relevance in ethnopharmacology and integrative medicine.

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